

1 **Identification of Menin as a component of an Xist solid tumor RNP complex.**

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7 We describe here identification of Menin, encoded by *Men1*, as a component of an Xist RNP complex
8 assembled in solid tumors in humans with cancer and human cells during transformation. Men1
9 expression was modestly activated in Xist+ embryonic stem cell clones and repressed in cells expressing
10 an Xist transgene. In p53-deficient breast cancer cells that feature Xist silencing as their defining
11 transcriptional feature, Men1 expression was also modestly activated. Proteomic analyses (published)
12 identified Men1 as an Xist-interacting protein. Men1 was transcriptionally co-regulated with Xist
13 localization factors SPEN and CIZ1, as well as recently identified Xist RNP complex components
14 KHDRBS1 and ILF3, together indicating Menin possesses a functional role in the Xist RNP in human
15 cancer.